

Federating Open Knowledge through Wikibase: The Case of The Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space

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Abstract

This paper presents the design and early implementation of the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space (DSS), a multilingual, community-driven prototype for linking cultural heritage data across institutional and geographic boundaries. Rather than a finished infrastructure, the DSS should be read as a blueprint and exploratory model – developed as a thought experiment with minimal resources but grounded in our prior work on music metadata governance involving both public and private actors. We use this experimental setting to review structural problems in existing Finno-Ugric knowledge systems: the negative outcomes of Wikipedia’s Livonian and Mari initiatives, the dispersion of diasporic knowledge, and the limitations of national GLAM infrastructures. Building on empirical literature and our own governance practice, we propose a lightweight federated infrastructure built on Wikibase and open ontologies, which enables multilingual vocabularies, contextual annotation, and ethical data linking without flattening local epistemologies. Case studies of Seto textile collections and the Hõimulõimed multilingual song archive illustrate how the prototype supports cultural reconstruction and participatory enrichment. While not an institutional solution, the DSS demonstrates how a semantically rich, community-anchored model can serve as a testbed for broader applications in low-scale cultural ecosystems.

Keywords

Wikibase, linked open data, Finno-Ugric heritage, multilingual metadata, digital infrastructure, interoperability, dress history, music data, data stewardship, research data management

1. Introduction

This paper introduces a multilingual, semantically structured approach to reconnecting fragmented Finno-Ugric cultural heritage. Our goal is to demonstrate how Linked Open Data (LOD) infrastructures – specifically Wikibase with the Lexeme extension – can be adapted to support endangered languages and low-scale cultural domains. We focus on communities such as the Setos, Võros, Livonians, and Maris, where heritage data is dispersed, weakly annotated, and poorly served by existing institutional systems.

We started by asking a deceptively simple question: *Where do we find Livonian, Mari, or Udmurt cultural data online?* The answer revealed major structural issues. Some materials are in commercial platforms like Spotify or YouTube but lack interoperability. Others sit in small, often offline museum collections. Even national GLAM infrastructures in Estonia, Latvia, Finland, and Hungary – despite

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their deep Finno-Ugric research history – publish metadata that is shallow, monolingual, and RDF-only, lacking persistent identifiers and multilingual vocabularies.

Our solution is the **Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space**, a lightweight, federated infrastructure that supports participatory metadata repair, semantic enrichment, and multilingual modelling. We don't aim to build another centralized repository; rather, we prototype a distributed and community-anchored model of linked open data – one that aligns with subsidiarity, interoperability, and epistemic equity. The sharper challenge in these contexts is not material restitution but epistemic access. Many communities cannot even read or review what has been collected about them. By explicitly disassociating from “ontological hijacking” and foregrounding epistemic justice, our model treats metadata as a medium of cultural repair rather than a static technical record.

Technically, our infrastructure connects CIDOC CRM-based museum records, DCTERMS-based library metadata, and Wikibase lexemes through shared patterns. But our deeper innovation lies in governance: we treat metadata as cultural expression, not technical scaffolding, and involve community actors as co-curators. This helps address what we term a semantic feedback failure – the lack of mechanisms for communities to revise and enrich institutional records. Importantly, the DSS is multi-sensory: it links clothing artefacts, songs, oral traditions, and images, showing how different cultural forms can be reassembled into a living infrastructure. Initial experiments with Võro Wikipedians, rural museums, and Wikimedia Eesti indicate that such reassembly is possible even at small scale, though sustained engagement requires further resources.

To stress-test our methodology, we focused on cases from Finno-Ugric communities such as the Setos, Võros, Livonians, and Mari groups. The idea for this work emerged at the *Wikimedia CEE Summit 2024*, where we considered whether Wikimedia technologies – particularly Wikibase with its Lexeme and semantic extensions – could support not just encyclopaedic documentation but also language preservation and cultural heritage stewardship in fragile knowledge ecosystems (Antal 2024). While Võro has maintained a presence on Wikipedia, other language editions like Livonian and Mari remain largely dormant. We hypothesized that aggregating culturally meaningful digital objects – songs, garments, photographs, and oral texts – might re-engage these communities by offering tangible points of entry for contribution and curation.

The screenshot shows the main page of the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space. The browser address bar displays the URL: `reprexbase.eu/fu/index.php?title=Main_Page`. The page has a blue header with a search bar and navigation links. The main content area is titled "Main Page" and contains a paragraph of introductory text, a "Contents" table of contents, and a "Collections" section. The "Collections" section is divided into "Musical works" and "Sound recordings", each with a list of specific collections and playlists.

Figure 1: The opening page at <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/index.php> for the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space

It is important to emphasize that what we present here is not a finished institutional infrastructure, but a working prototype and blueprint. The DSS functions as a conceptual and technical testbed – developed

with minimal resources – to explore governance models, semantic tools, and participatory practices that could later be scaled up within larger institutional or community-driven projects.

The paper proceeds as follows: we first describe the conceptual foundations of our approach and its origins in music metadata work. We then show how this model was extended to textile heritage through the **TextileBase** project. Our two main case studies – traditional Seto and Livonian clothing – demonstrate how multilingual thesauri, reconciled place names, and participatory tooling can expose meaningful cultural patterns across semantically shallow collections. Finally, we reflect on the broader applicability of this methodology and propose a more ambitious vision for cultural interoperability, grounded in the *8-star linked open data model*.

2. Methodology

Our methodology balances bottom-up reconstruction with top-down alignment. We began with a culturally rooted Seto exhibition, combining photographs, garments, and metadata from Estonian, Finnish, and Hungarian collections. This bottom-up demonstration shows that meaningful cultural reconstruction is possible even without standardized institutional metadata, while also feeding into upstream vocabularies in an iterative loop. Grounded in a community-first principle, our approach assumes that low-scale heritage systems require intentional structuring to ensure visibility and stewardship.

We treat metadata as an epistemic artifact, not a neutral scaffold. Following Caswell (2016), who reminds us that “description is power,” and Bowker and Star (1999), who show how classification systems embed institutional perspectives, we recognize that even seemingly technical schemas like the *Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus*® (AAT) or CIDOC CRM make ontological commitments about what counts as a person, object, or relationship (Bekiari et al. 2024). This dynamic can result in what we term ontological hijacking: the reuse of established schemas in ways that unintentionally misrepresent or erase community-specific meanings. To counter this, we design alternative linkage and annotation patterns that enable recontextualization – grounded not in external taxonomies, but in the perspectives of speakers, custodians, and domain experts from within the communities themselves. We also draw conceptual support from the *European Interoperability Framework* (EIF), which we detail further in section 3.1. Originally designed for cross-border public services within the EU – “to provide better, more user-focused public services to citizens” (European Commission 2017) – EIF is also the underlying interoperability framework for the *European Open Science Cloud* (EOSC) and, by extension, the *Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities* (DARIAH-EU). Yet this connection is often overlooked: researchers and digital humanists tend to discuss FAIR data principles as if data interoperability were a goal in itself, rather than a means of enabling interoperable services across collections and research applications. We therefore prototype a service that aspires to a higher level of interoperability than the individual open data sources on which it builds. For us, the legal, organisational, and semantic layers defined by EIF are not compliance checkboxes, but the terrain of ethical service design – where infrastructure becomes a vehicle for stewardship rather than mere publication. To operationalize our approach, we developed a simple typology of scale to identify structurally underserved communities. By “scale” we mean measurable factors such as number of speakers, archival depth, institutional presence, and degree of self-representation in digital systems. On this basis, groups such as the Setos, Võros, Livonians, and Votians function within low-scale heritage ecosystems: culturally rich but institutionally weak, with little influence over the curatorial policies of state collections.

This imbalance is especially visible in the foundational periods of national museums and ethnographic collections in Estonia, Latvia, Finland, and Hungary. These institutions articulated majority national identities, while smaller “kindred peoples” were framed as exotic or peripheral. In Finland, for example, Karelian storytelling traditions were appropriated into the Finnish national epic Kalevala. Comparable dynamics shaped the incorporation of Livonians in Latvia, Szeklers in Hungary,

and Võros and Setos in Estonia – cases where majority nation-building appropriated minority heritage while simultaneously marginalizing it. These collections also emerged within imperial frameworks – Finland and Hungary as semi-autonomous territories of the Russian and Habsburg empires, and Estonia and Latvia within the Russian Empire – so nation-building both resisted empire and homogenized local cultures.

The Livonian case illustrates how these dynamics persisted into the 20th century. Although Latvia’s constitutional recognition of Livonian heritage is a meaningful step toward redress, Livonian materials were historically collected and classified by Russians, Finns, and later Latvians and Estonians. Under both imperial and Soviet conditions, ethnographers used their own categories and priorities, so names, terminologies, and cultural meanings were often flattened, misunderstood, or lost.

Our methodology responds to these structural gaps by reconnecting collections and metadata from systems with limited formal memory, low documentation density, and fragmented coverage; and, where possible, by incorporating private collections and informal or tacit knowledge. Communities such as Seto and Võro, with populations ranging from 1,500 to 40,000, are numerically smaller than European microstates like Iceland or Malta – but unlike those nations, they lack national cultural institutions of their own. Others, such as the Livonians or Votians, are moribund, with preservation efforts driven by a handful of activists, scholars, or partial speakers. These dynamics resonate with broader critiques of how dominant institutions appropriate or overwrite minority heritage. Tuhiwai-Smith (2007) describes this as “research through imperial eyes,” where external taxonomies flatten local epistemologies, while Rastas (2005) highlights how minority cultural expressions are subsumed into majority narratives. Such insights sharpen our understanding of why Finno-Ugric materials remain shallowly documented and externally framed, and why methodological repair requires more than technical linking.

At first glance, our case studies may seem simple. In one, we connected clothing history material from three rural museums in Setomaa to a fourth, already digitized collection in Saatsse, and extended this network into Estonian, Finnish, Latvian, and Hungarian national systems. In the other, we began with folk and contemporary music playlists – manually curated on Spotify – and attempted to align them with structured cultural data. Yet the methodological challenges we faced are not unique to minority contexts: many national systems also suffer from shallow modelling, poor linking, and monolingual metadata. Linking datasets across domains, institutions, and languages proved far more difficult than the 5-star FAIR model suggests. In practice, findability, interoperability, and reuse are rarely achieved across heterogeneous vocabularies and heritage-specific contexts. For this reason, we adopted the extended 8-star model of linked cultural data proposed by Hyvönen and Tuominen (2024), which adds essential dimensions such as provenance, multilingualism, contextualization, participation, and sustainability. This higher standard better reflects the realities of cross-border, community-anchored heritage work and informs every layer of our infrastructure – from ontology design and multilingual label support to governance and long-term maintenance. Alongside FAIR and the *8-star model*, we also considered the *CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance* (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) (Carroll et al. 2020). These were formulated in Indigenous contexts such as North America and Oceania, but they raise important questions for Finno-Ugric heritage. The situations here are heterogeneous: Hungarians, Finns, Estonians, and Latvians have nation-states with strong institutional infrastructures; Setos, Võros, and Livonians are integrated autochthonous groups with limited cultural institutions; while most Finno-Ugric peoples in the Russian Federation face sharply declining rights and protections.

This diversity makes it difficult to map CARE directly onto post-imperial European contexts. Unlike settler-colonial settings, where material restitution and cultural restrictions are central, the sharper issue here is epistemic access: many communities cannot even read or review what has been collected about them. Our DSS experiments with applying aspects of CARE – such as multilingual metadata accessibility, cultural reassembly, and safe avenues for community review – but we also see the need to revise or extend these principles to account for communities like the Livonians, Setos, or Szeklers,

whose circumstances differ from both Indigenous sovereignty movements as well as the problems of “kindred peoples” in the Russian Federation.

In this sense, CARE is less a ready-made framework than an invitation to further research: how might principles of collective benefit, authority, and responsibility be re-thought for communities shaped by the dual legacy of imperial rule and nation-state homogenisation? We cannot yet answer this fully, but we believe our work highlights the importance of asking the question.

This suggests that our approach, although inspired by Finno-Ugric cases, may be broadly applicable – especially in non-English language contexts or under-resourced digital infrastructures. In the sections that follow, we describe the technical and conceptual tools we used to build a multilingual, multimodal infrastructure capable of supporting cultural reconstruction at small scale but with broader implications.

2.1. Semantic Layering and Ontological Patterns

Our work builds on a foundational insight from early Semantic Web development: knowledge graph architectures can be conceptualized as a “layer cake” (Mayank, Craig A., and Pedro, 2021). This model presents semantic infrastructure as a structured stack – from URIs and Unicode at the base, through RDF and ontology layers (RDFS, OWL), and upward to querying, reasoning, and user-facing applications. While vocabularies such as AAT or CIDOC CRM occupy key positions in this middle semantic layer, they often reflect Western institutional logics and lack vocabulary for culturally embedded domains like Finno-Ugric clothing, toponymy, or oral traditions.

One complication is the illusion of standardization in CIDOC CRM. Though presented as a formal ontology for cultural heritage, it functions more as a flexible modelling dialect. At version 7.2, CIDOC CRM has its own evolving history (Bekiaris et al. 2024). Its application depends heavily on local priorities (e.g., emphasis on provenance vs. object description), available expertise, software tooling, and legacy data. Many datasets were not updated with new ontology releases, resulting in what might be called a vernacular CIDOC – technically shared, yet semantically divergent. Even collections that claim CRM conformance frequently require reconciliation, especially across national or institutional boundaries. Platforms like Finna.fi and Muis.ee demonstrate relatively coherent implementation across Finnish and Estonian sources but integrating Hungarian or Latvian data introduces substantial modelling friction.

Archival data adds further complexity. Many archives are still transitioning from legacy standards such as ISAD(G) to CIDOC-inspired frameworks like *Records in Context* (RiC). Semantic reconciliation here is especially fragile, and full harmonization is often impractical (Archives Expert Group on Archival Description 2023).

In response, we emphasize **modular ontological patterns** over rigid global alignment. Drawing from the eXtreme Design methodology – originally developed in open-source software design and recently applied in the Polifonia ontology family for music – we identify reusable semantic fragments that support meaningful cross-domain linking (Blomqvist, Hammar, and Presutti 2016; Berardinis et al. 2023). While some scholars warn against “ontological hijacking” – the cherry-picking of classes or properties to fit local models – we aim to formalize recurring, low-friction patterns that emerge in vernacular use across systems like AAT or Wikidata.

We do not suggest that national systems are flawed. Finnish, Estonian, Latvian, and Hungarian infrastructures serve their cultural missions and their user base well. But building a “Seto national” or “Livonian national” collection means operating across these infrastructures – often without the benefit of a central institutional home. In this context, multilingual thesauri and repeatable modelling patterns act as connective tissue, providing just enough semantic scaffolding to support cultural reassembly.

To this end, we revisit classic tools from early Semantic Web discourse – gazetteers, multilingual term mapping, and seed ontologies – but repurpose them with attention to marginality, sovereignty, and situated knowledge. While originally developed for place names, we adapt the gazetteer model to ambiguous cultural terms. Loosely defined entities like “shirt” or “brooch” are anchored to stable

identifiers in AAT and enriched with domain-specific details. A “Seto women’s shirt,” for example, becomes a subclass of “shirt,” further specified by gender, cultural group, and ritual context using community-informed vocabularies.

This positions our work at a key inflection point in the Semantic Web stack: the interface between general-purpose ontologies and community-specific modelling. We do not aim to replace existing standards, but to supplement them – offering ways for low-scale, underrepresented knowledge systems to participate in linked data infrastructures without flattening their epistemic diversity.

While our techniques – semantic reconciliation, multilingual labelling, and modular modelling – may appear modest, their practical value lies in real-world applicability. Unlike many prototype-driven digital heritage projects, our infrastructure is designed for long-term sustainability and integration. It explicitly includes governance strategies, multilingual support, and contextual sensitivity as part of its technical architecture.

To go beyond digital curation, we adopt the European Interoperability Framework not only as a semantic guide but also as a legal and organizational model (Commission and Digital Services 2017; European Commission 2017). In Finno-Ugric contexts, this involves bridging institutional archives with community-held collections – family photographs, oral recordings, handwritten lexica – that are often invisible in national or disciplinary systems. Our framework enables structured interconnection while respecting privacy, sovereignty, and community-specific interpretive authority.

A precedent for this lies in the *Slovak Comprehensive Music Database*, where EIF principles supported the reuse of metadata from platforms like Spotify and YouTube. Even when recordings are rights-restricted, core metadata such as performer names, titles, or durations is often available for scholarly linkage. We incorporate this data into a multimodal knowledge graph – not to redistribute content, but to support discovery, rights tracking, and cross-contextual interpretation.

As Park and Tosaka observe, metadata creators often prioritize usability over schema compliance, constrained by institutional tooling, staff capacity, and context-specific needs (Park and Tosaka 2010). This leads to semantically similar but formally divergent datasets – particularly across the boundary between public institutions and commercial systems. For example, song titles and performer names appear in both music industry standards (e.g., standards set by the DDEX organisation in music) and cultural heritage schemas (e.g., DCTERMS, CIDOC CRM), but encode distinct assumptions about rights, roles, and reuse.

As Pomerantz reminds us, “what is considered data and what is metadata is largely a matter of your point of view” (Pomerantz 2015). A field considered central in one domain may be auxiliary in another. Metadata is never neutral; it reflects the institutional logics and epistemic assumptions of its designers. Translation layers are therefore not merely technical – they are interpretive tools that expose these embedded worldviews. To navigate such complexity, we adopt a modular strategy: linking small, interoperable segments drawn from DDEX, RiC, CIDOC, and DCTERMS.

This lightweight, pattern-based approach is especially effective for shallow or inconsistent data. In Finnish, Latvian, Estonian, and Hungarian collections, metadata is often monolingual, underspecified, or applied with local variations. Rather than depending on AI-based inference, we develop simple, human-centered tools that support multilingual, cross-institutional, and diasporic metadata enrichment.

In practice, the most effective anchors for discovery are names – of places, ethnolinguistic groups, cultural figures (e.g., Hilda Grīva, Hilana Taarka), or collectors (e.g., Aladár Bán, Axel Olai Heikel). These entities transcend variable metadata quality and become key levers for reconstructing fragmented cultural memory across national systems.

2.2. Multilingual Geographic Reconciliation

We began by constructing a multilingual geographic reconciliation layer – a gazetteer – to align historical and modern place names across scripts and languages. Unlike standard geocoding, our approach integrates historical variants and is manually verified with Finno-Ugric scholars to ensure

cultural nuance. As a prototype, we focused on the Livonian coast, where a dozen villages retained Livonian into the early 20th century. Using the *Livonian Place Name Catalogue* (Ernštreits 2020), we mapped names across Livonian, Latvian, Estonian, Finnish, Hungarian, Russian, and Baltic German.

This layering improves discovery in collections that use inconsistent or outdated toponyms. For instance, Mazirbe (Livonian: Irē) appears variously as *Klein-Irben*, *Vähä Irben*, or *Irai*. Such linguistic and political shifts – from German exonyms to Soviet-standard Latvian forms – illustrate why rigid normalization is impractical (Antal, Mester, and Pigozne 2025). Our work draws on and extends existing approaches. Wikibase has proven effective for multilingual authority control (Bianchini, Bargioni, and Pellizzari di San Girolamo 2021; Fagervig 2023) and working with standardised and non-standardised minority languages. The long-term collaboration between the *National Library of Wales* and *Wikimedia UK* demonstrates an institutional model, where stable funding, government reporting, and professional staff enabled large-scale image sharing and the creation of bilingual authority files (Evans 2025). By contrast, the *Wikimedians of Võro User Group* illustrates a hybrid path of standardisation, with some institutional support via *Wikimedia Eesti* and the *Võro Institute* which is itself a language standardisation body, but with a much smaller institutional footprint than the Welsh government bodies (Wikimedians of Võro language User Group 2025). A third model is represented by Wikimedia Norge’s Sámi knowledge project, which foregrounded community-based authority through advisory groups and partnerships with Sámi institutions, embedding respect for knowledge sovereignty and multilingual representation (Wikimedia Norge 2020). Together, these examples highlight how multilingual reconciliation can be anchored in institutional infrastructures, in semi-formalised volunteer structures, or in community-led networks. Our DSS generalises these lessons to dispersed Finno-Ugric contexts, where governance must be federated across institutions, communities, and borders.

Setomaa posed a larger challenge than the Livonian coast. Although culturally cohesive, it includes more than 150 settlement names in Estonia alone – and many more in Russia, where the remaining Seto population is largely assimilated (Herran 2025). We selectively added high-priority sites from *Pskov Oblast*, where metadata uses multiple names (e.g., Pskov appearing as *Pleskau*, *Pihkva*, or *Pleskava*). Rather than forcing premature standardisation, we treat such ambiguity as a signal that guides enrichment. This bottom-up approach helps us decide which variants support discovery and which introduce noise. The resulting gazetteer aids both provenance repair and multilingual discovery. It is replicable and can be extended to other multilingual regions such as Latgale in Latvia or the Khanty-Mansi areas of Siberia by combining public sources with community expertise.

2.3. Thesaurus and Ontology Patterns

We developed a multilingual thesaurus for Finno-Ugric garments, using the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus® (AAT) as a scaffold (Harpring et al. 2020). While originally designed for American collections, AAT has been enriched through international collaborations such as the Portuguese extension (Silva 2022). In our case, we did not formally adhere to the Getty Institute’s translation protocols; instead, we created label-level translations (not scope notes) in Estonian, Finnish, Latvian, Hungarian, and – when possible – Livonian. We treated the AAT’s embedded conceptual structure as an ontological scaffold, preserving upper-level categories such as *shirt* or *upper-body garment*, and introducing culturally specific subclasses beneath them – for example, the Seto *kitasnik* pinafore dress and the conical brooch (*kuhiksõlg* / *mellboglár*). While the AAT’s current structure does not yet accommodate the full diversity of Finno-Ugric material culture, it remains a pragmatic framework for cross-institutional alignment, particularly for locating diasporic items in Western museum collections. Ethnographic metadata is often shallow or ambiguous. Phrases like “Seto girl in traditional costume” or generic terms such as “shirt” obscure cultural specificity. Some objects labelled as “women’s shirts” turn out to be men’s clothing, without gender or ceremonial context. To address this, we repurposed the gazetteer model: generic terms such as *shirt*, *skirt*, or *shoe* were anchored to AAT identifiers, while

subclasses such as “Seto women’s shirt” were enriched with gender, group, and ritual context. This balances broad discovery with ontological precision: generic terms support search, while specialist vocabularies enable cultural reassembly.

The brooch illustrates this challenge. In Finnish records it is often labelled *solki* (clasp); in Hungarian, *mellboglár*; in Seto usage, *kuhiksõlg*; or appears unlabeled in photographs. Without reconciliation, these remain disconnected (Museum of Ethnography, n.d.; National Museum of Finland, n.d.; Väisänen 1912; Eesti Rahva Muuseum, n.d.; Eesti Ajaloomuuseum 1912). Our thesaurus aligns them within one conceptual structure, supporting cross-institutional and multilingual integration.

Methodologically, our approach aligns with “ontology seeding” (Pazienza et al. 2012; Pazienza and Stellato 2012; Pazienza, Stellato, and Vindigni 2012), where semi-automated term extraction is followed by expert correction. This addresses what they call the “knowledge acquisition bottleneck” while preserving cultural specificity. The approach also resonates with EU guidelines for trustworthy AI, which emphasise transparency, human oversight, and contextual adaptation (European Commission and Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology 2019; European Parliament and Council 2024). Instead of replacing standards, we enrich them: refining vague labels, resolving cultural ambiguities, and linking vernacular terms to formal ontologies. Computational tools may assist at scale, but expert-guided, multilingual modelling remains central in cultural heritage.

2.4. Automation Perspectives

Some components of our workflow could be substantially improved and partially automated using computational linguistics and inference engines. Projects in digital humanities have demonstrated the value of semantic annotation, named entity recognition, and multilingual knowledge graph construction for analyzing under-documented languages and collections (Fiorucci et al. 2020; Münster and Terras 2019). However, small communities often face barriers in applying these methods due to lack of tools and access (Jehangir, Radhakrishnan, and Agarwal 2023). Moreover, relying on state-of-the-art natural language processing methodology inevitably runs the risk of decreasing factual correctness, and might prove to be challenging with low-resource minority languages. Therefore, a delicate balance needs to be found between creating more data by automating processes and preserving the reliability of our methodology.

Let us imagine a scenario where a humanities researcher wants to browse and retrieve elements from a set of Finno-Ugric collections using relevant keywords in a given (Finno-Ugric or majority) language. The three main challenges we face in this setting are:

- low-quality or missing metadata
- descriptions in a different language
- descriptions that are inconsistent (e.g. not in the expected language or register, irrelevant or incorrect vocabulary)

To deal with these different types of difficulties that can co-occur in the same item, several problems need to be overcome. User queries should be aligned to a pivot (meta- or restricted natural) language, and the vocabulary of this language needs to be organised in a structured thesaurus or a basic ontology. Terms that are too specific and/or obsolete need to be translated to a current, more generic terminology. In this context, the creation of multilingual gazetteers can be partially automated where existing resources and relevant vocabulary provided by humanities scholars serve as a seed for well-resourced languages (typically majority or official languages), while the extension to lesser resourced languages can be facilitated through automated synonym detection and cross-lingual term alignment.

This terminology can later be enriched with basic relations that can serve as filters to exclude unlikely or contradictory query results. Structuring the gazetteers into a domain ontology can in turn benefit from language technology methods. On the one hand, large language models, while often lacking

reliable domain-specific expertise, can efficiently contribute to anchor terms in a common ontology in both monolingual and multilingual settings. Adding domain-specific semantic relation types can be aided by unsupervised acquisition methods (García-Mendoza et al. 2024). However, producing reliable metadata will ultimately require the judgment of a humanities researcher: the usefulness of a given annotation and metadata scheme is to be evaluated with respect to their impact on the research studies to be carried out on the data. In that sense, we consider our method a form of digitally supported humanities research, rather than fully automated digital humanities.

2.5. Language-Independent Multimodal Inference

Where linguistic metadata proves insufficient, we turn to multimodal content analysis to support identification and linkage across fragmented archives. Our system combines structured linguistic metadata – using Wikibase Lexemes – with language-independent similarity tools such as the International Standard Content Code (ISCC) and acoustic fingerprinting (ISO 2024).

ISCC enables robust, content-based linking by encoding intrinsic properties of media files. This allows us to detect near-duplicates or variants of the same item across institutions and platforms, regardless of differences in naming, metadata, or file structure. For instance, a user uploading a traditional song or photo of a textile object need not recall its original title or language – ISCC permits high-confidence matching based on the content itself.

This approach was especially valuable in our analysis of recurring musical motifs in Livonian recordings, where titles were inconsistent and metadata sparse. By combining acoustic similarity, volunteer tagging, and visual motif matching, we identified meaningful clusters across poorly annotated materials – surfacing patterns that would otherwise remain buried.

Importantly, this strategy reduces dependency on high-quality metadata without erasing linguistic or cultural differences. Instead of normalizing local variation into a global schema, it enables a bottom-up form of inference, where discovery is grounded in the properties of the materials themselves. This aligns with our overall goal of supporting epistemic diversity while enhancing interoperability.

Such multimodal inference tools extend the archival surface: making cultural items accessible to users without institutional privileges or complete linguistic knowledge, while still respecting the specificity of low-scale heritage ecosystems. In this sense, language-independent similarity operates not as a replacement for metadata, but as a complementary layer that reinforces inclusive discovery and repair.

3. Governance, Interoperability, and the Cultural Data Space Model

The *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space* was developed in parallel with, and informed by, earlier linked open data projects: the **Open Music Observatory**, the **Slovak Comprehensive Music Database (SKCMDb)**, and **TextileBase**. These initiatives demonstrated that decentralised metadata governance – when grounded in legal, organisational, semantic, and technical alignment – can serve both institutional and community needs. The current work extends those strategies to a new domain: the heritage of ethnic groups lacking national heritage institutions and, often, standardised written languages.

Rather than centralising metadata into a single repository, our approach follows the data sharing space model outlined in the European Interoperability Framework, also adopted by the European Open Science Cloud and DARIAH (Commission and Digital Services 2017).

3.1. The Data Sharing Space Approach

Our infrastructure is designed as a data sharing space rather than a centralised data lake. Instead of aggregating all content into a single repository, data remains with its original custodians and is

connected through shared standards and interfaces. This federated approach is particularly suitable in contexts where enforcing unified schemas or common legal contracts is impractical (Curry 2020; EBU and Gaia-X 2022, p. 16), for example, when some custodians are public entities like the Estonian National Museum or the Finnish National Museum, while others are private non-governmental organisations. This data sharing space aligns well with the principles of the European Interoperability Framework developed for truly interoperable digital services (Commission and Digital Services 2017; Nagel and Lycklama 2021) and mirrors the architectural logic adopted by the European Open Science Cloud and DARIAH: enabling standards-based, controlled interconnection while preserving institutional autonomy and local data governance.

The EIF defines interoperability as a four-layered construct:

- Legal: shared rights and licensing principles
- Organisational: aligned institutional workflows
- Semantic: interoperable meanings across vocabularies and languages
- Technical: standard formats, APIs, and protocols

In practice, most of the heritage we handle concerns deceased persons, and we work with metadata or digital surrogates rather than original collections. This differs from contexts where decolonisation debates focus on material repatriation or sacred heritage. Legally, our DSS is governed by European author's rights (rather than the copyright systems assumed in much of the decolonisation literature) and by GDPR, which together provide comparatively strong protection for creators' integrity and personal data.

Where these frameworks do not apply – particularly for Finno-Ugric communities in the Russian Federation, where legal protections are absent and open participation may expose individuals to risk – we look to the *CARE Principles* (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, Ethics) as an ethical complement to EIF. While CARE was formulated in Indigenous contexts outside Europe, it highlights the importance of ensuring that the communities benefit from, and retain authority over, how they are represented. Our governance model therefore combines the binding legal frameworks of the EU with non-binding but vital community-centred ethics, adapted to the different situations of Finno-Ugric peoples.

We draw on the *Big Data Value Association's* position paper (EBU and Gaia-X 2022) to structure our infrastructure according to these layers. Interoperability, in this model, is not achieved merely by RDF serialization but by creating systems where metadata is editable, attributable, and reusable – technically, semantically, and socially.

The *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space* serves as a governance testbed for this model. It is not controlled by a single institution but maintained collaboratively across national and community actors. This setup enables experimental workflows such as multilingual reannotation and non-authoritative linking – practices crucial in post-imperial, underrepresented cultural contexts. By enabling researchers, GLAM professionals, and community stakeholders to co-curate and refine records, we aim to model a governance structure rooted in subsidiarity and epistemic equity.

This multi-level, federated design also allows for trust to be rebuilt – between disparate collection systems, between curators and users, and between ethnic communities and heritage custodians. Rather than centralising cultural authority, we distribute it in a way that supports long-term stewardship and sustainable enrichment of composite datasets.

Our work also extends lessons from other minority-language and GLAM collaborations. The long-term partnership between the National Library of Wales and Wikimedia UK exemplifies an *institutional model* where stable funding and government reporting enabled the creation of bilingual authority files and large-scale image sharing (Evans 2025). By contrast, the *Wikimedians of Võro User Group* represents a grassroots model, reliant on volunteer activity and partial institutional support from *Wikimedia Eesti* and the *Võro Institute* (Wikimedians of Võro language User Group 2025). The Sámi

knowledge online project coordinated by Wikimedia Norge illustrates a community-led model, embedding respect for knowledge sovereignty and multilingualism through advisory groups and partnerships (Wikimedia Norge 2020). Finally, the Wiki for Minorities programme’s Greenland project highlights a **content-survival model**, aimed at sustaining a small Wikipedia edition and preserving language visibility under risk of closure (Wiki for Minorities Programme 2024). These precedents demonstrate that no single governance template exists: infrastructures may be institutional, volunteer-driven, community-based, or survival-oriented. The Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space adapts elements of each but emphasizes a federated model, where authority is distributed across institutions and communities rather than centralised in one locus.

At the DHNB 2025 “Dreams” conference, where this paper was first presented, we received valuable feedback from the Sampo team and the broader digital humanities community. Seeing the advantages of the Sampo-UI interface in multiple use cases, we decided to complement our Wikibase endpoint with a Fuseki triplestore and a Sampo-UI front end, creating a Wikibase–Fuseki–Sampo binding. Given the increasing adoption of both Wikibase Suite and Sampo-UI in digital humanities (Hyvönen 2022), this integration provides a useful pathway for similar projects aiming at sustainable linked data infrastructures. The semantic browser of our data sharing space contents can be reviewed at <https://finnougric.net>.

3.2. Precedents in Music and Textile Metadata

The **Open Music Observatory (OMO)** was our first implementation of this approach. Informed by the *Feasibility Study for the Establishment of a European Music Observatory* (Commission et al. 2020) and supported by the OpenMusE project (Open Music Europe 2023), OMO addressed fragmented music metadata ecosystems – spanning digital distributors, rights management organisations, and streaming platforms – through a federated model of national and regional nodes. These include **SKCMDb** and a **Finno-Ugric** federated music node focused on popular and folk music by Finno-Ugric communities without national representation.

A dedicated OpenMusE work package examined the “observatory” concept as a modern infrastructure: not a monolithic system, but a distributed monitoring environment. From the outset, working with music forced us to grapple with multimodality: much metadata is embedded in sound files, not texts.

TextileBase extended this capacity to tangible cultural heritage. It focused on traditional dress and textiles, where sources are inherently visual and often poorly annotated. Here, we refined our methods for semantic linking between material artefacts, illustrations, and textual documentation – especially in the absence of harmonised institutional metadata.

One output of this work is the dataset *Linked Open Datasets on Traditional Livonian Clothing*, published as part of the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space* (Pigozne et al. 2025). It provides structured metadata and visual documentation of Livonian garments across national collections, offering a reference point for comparative research in dress history and cultural heritage studies.

3.3. Finno-Ugric Heritage as Stress Test

These prior experiences culminated in the *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space*, which we are validating through Seto, Livonian, and Mari cultural domains. These cases are not united by geography or object similarity, but by linguistic proximity and shared identity within the Finno-Ugric language family.

In the humanities, much knowledge remains coded in natural language – often in non-standardised or archaic forms. Interoperability between unstructured texts and structured databases remains a critical challenge. Linguistic diversity complicates metadata harmonisation: for example, reading field notes by A. O. Heikel or Aladár Bán from over a century ago demands interpretive flexibility.

To support under-standardised languages like Livonian, Seto, or Meadow Mari, we integrated the *Wikibase Lexeme* extension, enabling structured representation of minority language data and variation.

3.4. Participatory Infrastructure and Semantic Feedback

Most heritage institutions expose only thin, accession-era metadata. Yet over decades, these objects have been studied in scholarly and community settings. The problem is not a lack of knowledge, but the absence of infrastructure to reintegrate it.

This project aggregates shallow metadata from Finnish, Estonian, Latvian, and Hungarian collections, and enables participatory annotation in Wikibase. Metadata is restructured into a living knowledge system – one that can evolve, be corrected, and be re-linked.

A compelling example is the rediscovery of Hilda Grīva (born Cerbaha), a bilingual Livonian–Estonian singer. Her archival recordings – once culturally suppressed – were semantically linked to newly created Wikidata and Wikipedia entries, legally clarified, and enriched with multilingual metadata. Her legacy, which includes the creation of a Livonian-Latvian-Esperanto dictionary, the foundation of the *Kāndla* ensemble and the recording of many traditional Livonian-language folk songs, was restored across platforms, including Spotify, and presented in multiple Finno-Ugric and European languages. This required transforming archival metadata into formats compatible with contemporary rights and distribution systems.

3.5. From Model to Principle: Cultural Data Spaces and Subsidiarity

From *Open Music Observatory* to *TextileBase* to *Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space*, a key principle has emerged: subsidiarity. Infrastructure should operate at the scale at which cultural meaning is produced. In our view, this is not merely a policy principle – it is an epistemological stance.

We propose a participatory, multilingual, semantically rich model of digital heritage infrastructure: one that does not centralise authority but distributes it; that does not flatten language, but makes variation legible; that does not treat metadata as a finished product, but as a medium for cultural repair.

4. Case Studies: Methodology in Practice

To evaluate the practical viability of our semantic infrastructure in fragmented cultural heritage contexts, we implemented two case studies. Both examples address key dimensions of the methodology: multilingual reconciliation, semantic inference, metadata enrichment, and multimodal curation. Importantly, each case was selected to reflect the practical difficulties described in our introduction – namely, poor metadata, dispersed collections, language fragmentation, and lack of institutional annotation from within the heritage community itself.

4.1. Case Study 1: Clothing and Visual Pattern Discovery Across Finno-Ugric Collections

This case study demonstrates the practical application of our multilingual thesaurus and geographic reconciliation model for targeted retrieval of clothing-related imagery and metadata. We focused specifically on locating visual and textual records of traditional clothing – such as Seto and Livonian shirts, aprons, and skirts – across Finnish, Estonian, and Hungarian museum databases.

We aimed to create two distinct datasets:

- A digital collection on Traditional Livonian Clothing, covering garments, accessories, and secondary descriptions from the 19th and early 20th centuries.

- A parallel dataset on Traditional Seto Clothing, assembled through both field and metadata-based methods.

Each dataset posed unique challenges.

The primary sources for traditional Livonian clothing are dispersed across museum collections in Latvia, Finland, and Estonia. Our open linked dataset focuses on artefacts accessible through Finnish and Estonian museums, since the holdings of the National History Museum of Latvia – which include skirts, aprons, shirts, caps, bodices, and accessories collected up to 1940 – cannot be published in open-access form due to museum policy. The earliest and richest collection is preserved at the National Museum of Finland, where the ethnographers Axel Olai Heikel and Emil Nestor Setälä documented and acquired more than one hundred garments during field expeditions in 1901–1902 and 1912, respectively. Their collections include rare items such as a red silk bodice and elements of bridal attire, reflecting clothing types first recorded by Anders Johan Sjögren in 1846 (Blumberga 2006). The next significant collection, comprising around forty garments, is housed at the National Museum of Estonia. Most of these items were acquired by the Estonian ethnographers Oskar Loorits in 1924–1925 and Ferdinand Linnus in 1928. The Livonian garments preserved in the Finnish and Estonian museums are therefore the earliest and most comprehensive material sources for reconstructing Livonian traditional dress, and they form the foundation for the linked records included in our dataset.

When Baltic German painter Julius Döring visited the Livonian coast in the 1840s, he noted that Livonians were culturally and linguistically distinct but not easily distinguished from Latvians by dress: “[The Livonians] appear to have a strong sense of their ethnic identity, and only in extremely rare cases do they marry someone of a different nationality. All of them also speak Latvian, and church services have been held in this language since ancient times. All those I saw differed little, or hardly at all, from Latvians in terms of clothing.” (Dērings 2016, p. 165)

This observation shaped our search strategy. We did not limit ourselves to identifying a “Livonian costume,” but rather sought any objects attributed to Livonians or linked geographically to the twelve inhabited and two abandoned Livonian villages on the **Northern Kurzeme** (Courland) coast. The ambiguity in visual differentiation underscores why building a digital surrogate collection requires geographic and ethno-linguistic filtering more than formal typology.

The situation was different for **Seto clothing**, where we hypothesize greater material distinctiveness from surrounding Russian and Estonian styles. However, assembling Seto records requires navigating a far more complex territorial and archival history.

As detailed in our methodology section, *Setomaa*’s borders have shifted repeatedly throughout the 20th century:

- under the Russian Empire, it was part of the Pskov Governorate;
- between 1920–1940, it belonged to independent Estonia as Petseri County, gained by the Treaty of Tartu;
- in 1945, the Soviet Union transferred most of Petseri County (including Petseri) to the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic, dividing Setomaa;
- after Estonia regained independence, only a portion – Setomaa Parish – remained in Estonia, within Võru County.

These shifts had demographic and archival consequences. Many Setos relocated to Estonia, often bringing heirlooms with them. But most foundational museum collections (e.g., from the National Museum of Finland, Estonian National Museum, and Hungary’s Museum of Ethnography) recorded provenance in what is now **Pskov Oblast**, Russia, rather than in the current Setomaa Parish.

As a result, assembling the Seto dataset involved visits to regional museums (Värška Farm Museum, Obinitsa Museum), consultations with Seto communities, and targeted metadata reconciliation – whereas the Livonian dataset was developed primarily through metadata review and two field visits.

Following the methodology outlined earlier, we used multilingual discovery terms from our thesaurus (e.g., *shirt*, *skirt*, *Setomaa*, *Liiviläiset*), combined with place names aligned through our gazetteer (e.g., *Setumaa*, *Kuurinmaa*, *Liivinranta*). We observed that localized search strings like *naisen paita Setumaa* (Finnish for “woman’s shirt Setomaa”) retrieved relevant records in the Finna aggregator, while their English equivalents returned none – highlighting the critical importance of language-specific discovery terms.

Geographic naming inconsistencies further complicated retrieval. Translated or archaic place names such as *Venäjä*, *Kuurinmaa*, *Liivinranta*, *Siikrog* (Finnish for “Russia, Courland, Livonian Coast, Sīkrags”) appeared in object provenance, revealing how multilingual reconciliation is vital for cross-historical and cross-linguistic metadata integration. Finally, when foreign place names or other attributes were inconsistently recorded or misspelt in museum metadata, searches based on the ethnographers’ names proved more reliable, as these were generally standardised and familiar to the cataloguing staff.

We also found structural limitations in the existing semantic models. In many RDF exports, image metadata lacked semantic depth. For example, *Seto naine rahvarõivais* (Estonian National Museum, n.d.) was treated as a generic photo, despite clearly depicting a **Seto kitasnik** (pinafore dress). Our model distinguishes between:

- the **representation** (the photograph);
- the **referent** (the garment);
- the **context** of institutional documentation (e.g., colour calibration cards).

Similarly, *ERM TM Fk 2001*, labelled *Setu rahvariities naine*, shows a woman in full Seto costume (Estonian National Museum, n.d.), yet the RDF export omits any modelling of the person, clothing elements, or ceremonial usage. Even with CIDOC CRM-based structuring, cultural detail is often lost. Our system supplements this with **semantic tagging** that identifies garments like *kitasnik*, *hame*, or *mellboglár* in multilingual and culturally grounded ways.

This case study confirms that:

- multilingual, culturally specific thesauri significantly improve discoverability;
- place name reconciliation across historical, linguistic, and political variants is essential;
- visual content must be semantically modelled to capture garment, person, and cultural context.

Our dual top-down and bottom-up approach – scaffolded by general ontologies, enriched by localized knowledge – proves effective even in semantically shallow and multilingual environments. The results of this work are published as three evolving datasets and corresponding data papers. Building on our foundational work in **TextileBase** (Pigozne, Antal, and Mester 2025), we applied the same LOD methodology to two new regions:

- Setomaa;
- Livonian Coast (Pigozne et al. 2025).

These datasets were developed through collaborative curation across dispersed museum records, regional fieldwork, and multilingual metadata sources. Unlike the Latgale dataset, which emerged from a long-term ethnographic research project, the new collections were built via targeted digital workflows and semantic modelling in partnership with regional experts and Wikidata contributors.

In collaboration with Wikimedia Eesti, we have also created two Wikipedia GLAM virtual exhibitions based on the datasets described above.

- Traditional Livonian Clothing (Pigozne, Antal, Federico 2025)
- Traditional Seto Clothing (Antal, Pigozne, Federico 2025)

The larger exhibition presents all traditional Livonian garments preserved in the Finnish and Estonian national museums, thereby bringing virtually together – for the first time – dispersed Livonian clothing artefacts and making them accessible to both the Livonian and Latvian communities in English and Latvian. The Seto exhibition, currently under construction, integrates garments and photographs from the Finnish and Estonian national museums, the collection of the Hungarian ethnographer Aladár Bán housed in Hungary, as well as items from local Seto museums documented during our field visits. These virtual exhibitions make the material readily accessible to both communities and researchers.

Our **toponymic infrastructure** is formalized in *Remapping the Livonian Coast: A Multilingual Gazetteer of the Settlements of Northern Kurzeme* (Antal, Pigozne, and Mester 2025), integrating variant place names from Livonian, Latvian, Estonian, Finnish, Russian, German, and Hungarian records with persistent GeoNames identifiers.

Together, these resources exemplify our commitment to modular, FAIR-compliant linked data practices and semantic inclusivity in Finno-Ugric cultural heritage modelling.

4.2. Case Study 2: Dream Motifs in Finno-Ugric Vocal Music

Regarding music, our goal was to include Finno-Ugric songs in the Data Sharing Space while avoiding the ethnomusicological pitfalls of labelling music by ethnonym. Although terms like “Hungarian” or “Samoyedic” are useful within folk music typologies, applying them too rigidly can reinforce narrow definitions of musical authenticity. Instead, we adopted a more contemporary cultural policy perspective. In media regulation and public broadcasting, many European countries apply local content quotas; we asked ourselves: *What would a curated music selection look like for a Livonian, or Mari audience today?*

This framing encouraged inclusion, especially for community members who might not be drawn to traditional folk or “world” music genres. Language became our primary selection criterion. If a song’s lyrics are in Livonian, for instance, it is inherently valuable for language learners and suitable for Seto or Livonian radio programming, regardless of genre.

The **Hõimulõimed Finno-Ugric Song Dataset** contains 2,025 vocal recordings with lyrics in Livonian, Karelian, Veps, Sámi, Khanti-Mansi, Komi, Mari, Udmurt, Erzyan, Moksha and Samoyedic languages, along with some Estonian, Finnish, and Hungarian examples. These contemporary and traditional – or rearranged – songs were collected by Britt-Kathleen Mere, Bogáta Timár, Agatha Murro, and other members of the Hõimulõimed cultural organization between July 2023 and early 2025. The dataset was subsequently enriched and uploaded into the Data Sharing Space.

The Finno-Ugric musical landscape is vibrant and evolving. It includes not only traditional material but also genres such as Nenets reggae, Seto death metal, Mari ethno-punk, and Udmurt folktronica. The collection was originally assembled with dissemination via Spotify and YouTube (Music) in mind – platforms that are widely accessible and popular. With the help of Finno-Ugric students, researchers, and activists, Hõimulõimed organized the material into curated playlists. Languages with a critical mass of material, such as Udmurt and Livonian, received dedicated playlists, while others (e.g., Võro and Seto; Erzyan and Moksha; Mari languages and the Samoyedic languages) were grouped together due to linguistic proximity or smaller corpus size.

To align with the theme of this conference – “**dreams**”, understood both as a noun (“an imaginary event while sleeping”) and a verb (“to dream”) – we developed a method for identifying thematic

content in multilingual music data. The ability to categorize texts across languages is a core application of the methodologies presented earlier.

Our process began with a seed set of dream-related lexemes (e.g., Hungarian *álom*, Finnish *uni*, Estonian *uni*, Livonian *uņ*) and their verbal forms (e.g., *álmodik*, *nägema und*, *näha und*). We then generated morphological variants, including:

- Singular/plural: *álmok*
- Possessive forms: *álmom*, *álmaid*, *álmai*, *álmaim*
- Locative cases: *álmomban*, *álmából*, *álmaimban*
- Verb forms: *álmodik*, *álmodtam*, *álmodnék*, *álmodtátok*

Table 1

Dream Motifs in Finno-Ugric Song Lyrics: Examples and Linguistic Analysis

Song Title	Lyrics Quotation	Explanation
тый мыйын омыштем (Mari)	“тый мыйын омыштем лият гын, мый тыйын воктекет чонгештылен миём шонем”	A love song where the partner appears in dreams. <i>омыштем</i> = “in my dreams”. Search lemma: ОМЫ-
Uyvötyñ (Udmurt)	“Öвӧл ни матын, тон нош – уйвӧтын / Уг уг луы отын киостэ кутын...”	A lament about loss, remembered through dreams. <i>уйвӧтын</i> = “in dreams”. Search lemma: уйвӧт
Tyloburdo (Udmurt)	“Тылобурдолэн кадь куаразэ... Уйвӧтам кылэм вал”	A springtime vision seen in a dream. <i>уйвӧтам</i> = “in my dreams”. Search lemma: уйвӧт
Unettomaan aikaan (Finnish)	<i>Unettomaan aikaan</i> (title)	Ambient song evoking sleeplessness and longing. <i>Unettomaan</i> = “in sleepless times”. Search lemma: une-
Igäine unohtus (Karelian)	“Buite kui unis, a ei ilmis...”	A meditation on death and oblivion. <i>unis</i> = “in a dream”. Search lemma: uni
Talvinõ unõlaul (Võro)	“Musjotada imä pöskõ / Selgä pandõ unõrõivad”	Lullaby describing the evening ritual. Search lemma: unõ
Омыштем ужам (Mari)	“Мый эше тым йӧратем / омыштем эре ужам”	Celebration of love present in dreams. <i>омыштем</i> = “in my dreams”. Search lemma: омы-
Gyöngyhajú lány (Hungarian)	“Igen él egy gyöngyhajú lány / Álmodtam vagy igaz talán”	Ambiguity between dream and reality. <i>álmodtam</i> = “I dreamed”. Search lemma: álmod-

This yielded 20–50 searchable surface forms per language. For instance, Imre Poniklo’s *Elefánt* features the line:

“*Megszoktam már, hogy az ágyamban / Helyetted csak pár álom van / egyre csak nőnek a kép-hegyek*”

Translated as:

“*I’ve grown used to lying without you in bed / with only a few images instead / A mountain of dreams is building up in my head.*”

Such examples demonstrate the challenge of conceptual alignment across languages: *kép-hegyek* (“mountains of images”) would be difficult to reconcile with AAT (Art & Architecture Thesaurus) terms.

We also tracked multi-word expressions that evade lemma-based search, such as *nägema und* (“to see a dream”) in Estonian or *álmot láttam* (“I saw a dream”) in Hungarian (Table 1).

This case illustrates how symbolic meaning (dreams) can be detected even in low-data environments. A user may not know the term *yüëöm*, but they may recognize it in a lyric or submit a fragment of a song. Through lemma-based linking, even partial matches become discovery points.

This case complements *Case Study 1* by extending our methodology into the auditory domain, showing that the same seeding, linking, and cultural contextualization model can be adapted to other media forms. In both cases, we work not with full metadata schemas or exhaustive vocabularies, but with lightweight, human-curated inferences – enough to build bridges between language, content, and cultural meaning.

5. Conclusion: Infrastructure as Cultural Repair

5.1. Origins and Cultural Repair

This project began as a thought experiment on the sidelines of the Wikimedia CEE 2024 conference, where Estonian, Finnish, and Hungarian Wikipedians and Wikibase technologists asked whether our data governance model and technological stack could offer an alternative to the Livonian and Mari Wikipedia incubators that had failed to grow in the past two decades (Antal 2024). We wanted to explore if open knowledge tools such as Wikibase and Lexemes could be repurposed not only for encyclopedic content but also for heritage stewardship, language preservation, and community engagement in fragile knowledge ecosystems. From this work emerged the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space (DSS): a distributed, multilingual infrastructure that supports participatory curation and cultural repair.

Building on this foundation, the DSS has now converged into the prototype *Wikimuuseum*, co-developed with Wikimedia Eesti and GLAM partners. Presented at Wikimedia CEE 2025 (Antal, Federico, Kruusamägi, and Pigozne 2025), it demonstrates how the DSS blueprint can evolve into a working, multilingual exhibition platform that reassembles dispersed heritage for endangered Finno-Ugric communities. This presentation also showcased how earlier outputs – such as the *Remapping the Livonian Coast* gazetteer (Antal, Pigozne, and Mester 2025) and the *Traditional Seto Clothing dataset* (Antal, Pigozne, and Federico 2025) – can be curated into a multilingual, cross-border virtual exhibition. By assembling material from Estonian, Finnish, Latvian, and Hungarian collections, the *Wikimuuseum* illustrates how dispersed Finno-Ugric heritage can be recontextualized through a federated, open infrastructure.

Our next endeavour will extend this model to Mari heritage. With the support of the Estonian National Museum and the Kindred People’s Programme, we are describing Mari objects and making them accessible in Meadow Mari, Russian, and English. This work highlights both ethical challenges – safe communication with Mari El under current conditions, and rapid language assimilation – and the possibilities of federated cultural infrastructures.

The exhibition model supports dialogic reassembly: curatorial authority is shared, feedback structurally enabled, and private collections allowed to enter public memory on local terms. Rather than enforcing dominant metadata schemas, these interventions reflect local epistemologies through multilingual annotation, culturally grounded reconciliation tools, and iterative feedback loops. As Anderson and Christen (2019) argue, conventional attribution practices in GLAM often reproduce exclusion, while Dinler (2025) critiques LOD for reinforcing epistemic hierarchies. Our choice of Wikimedia as a platform – and the protections offered by our standalone Wikibase – illustrates how

participatory infrastructures can mitigate these risks and make linked data a medium of stewardship rather than extraction.

5.2. Epistemic Visibility

We define *epistemic visibility* as the ability of communities to see themselves – and be seen – in the cultural record. Visibility cannot be achieved by representation alone but requires structural legibility: multilingual labels, context-rich annotations, and governance models that allow peripheral voices to shape their own data narratives. Many items in our dataset already exist in public collections, yet without language-specific metadata, they remain invisible to those best placed to interpret them. By enabling shared authorship grounded in local knowledge, the DSS makes these reconnections possible.

This is not only a technical achievement but an ethical stance: metadata systems determine whose knowledge is credible and whose heritage is actionable. Our experiments suggest that infrastructures designed with openness, multilingual annotation, and participatory enrichment can foster epistemic justice in ways that conventional GLAM practices have rarely achieved.

5.3. Future Work and Broader Impact

This project began as an exploratory collaboration between four researchers, not a funded institutional programme. Working within existing occupations and grants, we visited rural museums, engaged with Võro Wikipedians, enriched Wikidata and Wikimedia Eesti, and began translations into Meadow Mari. While modest, these experiments showed that meaningful cultural reconstruction is possible at small scale if licensing, semantic gaps, and notability rules are navigated with care. The reception – from local museums, Wikimedia Eesti, and community members – was encouraging.

One area of tangible impact is comparative dress history. Linking garments, visual documentation, and ethnographic records created semantically rich datasets that support new research into craft networks, social structures, and cultural change. This work was mostly manual, but it laid the foundation for carefully integrated automation. Over the course of a year, we advanced from curated playlists to the most comprehensive dataset on Livonian dress history to date – demonstrating how manual groundwork can enable sustainable pipelines.

Technically, the DSS now operates on a **Wikibase–Fuseki–Sampo stack**, complemented by the Lexeme extension and graph-aligned models. This ensures pragmatic alignment across datasets while safeguarding trust and community confidence. Our aim is not only inclusion but shared curatorial authority: infrastructures where cultural data is collaboratively maintained and semantically accountable.

At a broader level, our prototype contributes to debates on epistemic justice. Unlike settler-colonial contexts, where restitution dominates, the sharper issue in Finno-Ugric heritage is epistemic access and voice. CARE principles require adaptation to post-imperial European contexts, where communities live modern, multilingual lives and must balance heritage review with pragmatic daily choices. DSS cannot guarantee revival, but it can provide recognition, memory, and possibility – ensuring that fragmented heritage remains accessible on community terms.

Finally, the methodology has applications well beyond digital curation. Parsing, repairing, and linking semi-structured data can benefit historical ecology, social sciences, or administrative archives. In this sense, the DSS is not only a cultural project but also a *prototype for infrastructural justice*: modest in scale, grounded in linked open data, and informed by epistemic humility.

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